

Ethics application

Method for interviews and focus groups: Understanding the current landscape of alternative publishing platforms

Aims and objectives

The project aims to explore the role and future of alternative platforms for publishing scholarly research. It will consider means to support innovation in scholarly communication through alternative publishing platforms, seeking insights into the maturity and development of existing and emerging examples. The research is commissioned by Knowledge Exchange, a coalition of six national organisations within Europe tasked with developing infrastructure and services to enable the use of digital technologies to improve higher education and research. The research will involve engagement with research funding organisations, developers of alternative publishing platforms and researchers, capturing lessons learned and recommendations likely to be of use to research funding organisations, publishing platforms and research-performing and research-supporting institutions. The project therefore has the potential to influence change in the scholarly publishing system at an international level. The project will be led and carried out by Research Consulting Ltd (based in Nottingham, UK), with Stephen Pinfield (University of Sheffield) acting as academic advisor.

Section A: Applicant details

Date application started:	
First name:	Stephen
Last name:	Pinfield
Generic research application:	No
Department:	Information School
Applying as:	Staff member
Research project title:	Innovating Scholarly Communication: Navigating the future of Alternative Publishing Platforms
Has your research project undergone academic review, in accordance with the appropriate process?	Yes

Section B: Basic information

Co-Applicants(s)

Name
Rob Johnson (Research Consulting LTD)
Andrea Chiarelli (Research Consulting LTD)
Katie Fraser (Research Consulting LTD)

Proposed project duration

Start date (of data collection):	Anticipated end date (of project)
Monday 31 st March 2025	26 th June 2026

Project code (where applicable)

Project externally funded?	Yes
Project code	Consultancy project

Suitability

Takes place outside of UK?	No
Involves NHS?	No
Health and/or social care human-interventional study?	No
ESRC funded?	No
Likely to lead to publication in a peer-reviewed journal?	Yes
Led by another UK institution?	No
Involves human tissue?	No
Clinical trial or a medical device study?	No
Involves social care services provided by a local authority?	No
Is social care research requiring review via the University Research Ethics Procedure	No
Involves adults who lack the capacity to consent?	No
Involves research on groups that are on the Home Office list of 'Proscribed terrorist groups or organisations'?	No

Indicators of risk

Involves partially vulnerable participants?	No
Involves potentially highly sensitive topics?	No

Section C: Summary of research

Methodology

This research project will involve a mix of semi-structured interviews and focus groups with a total of about 40 international stakeholders in scholarly communications. These activities will engage research funding organisations, developers of alternative publishing platforms and researchers.

Semi-structured one-to-one or small group (up to three participants, if required) interviews will take place with 8-10 representatives of research funding organisations and 10-15 researchers. These in-depth conversations will be critical to understand the functionalities, maturity and developments of alternative publishing platforms. Our interviews will also seek to explore the most promising areas for recommendations and future activities in this space.

Additionally, two focus groups will take place with around 4-8 representatives of alternative publishing platforms each. These will be based on interactive discussion between the participants and will help us investigate the motivations of alternative publishing platforms as well as the challenges that they aim to address. During the focus group, we will discuss some of the findings that emerged from the semi-structured interviews, to compare and contrast views from service providers (the alternative publishing platforms) and their intended users and audience.

We will use interviews and focus groups to explore the following research questions:

- Which approaches do research funders apply towards alternative publishing platforms, and how important are they in the context of funders' wider scholarly communication strategies?
- What types and formats of publication do funders and researchers consider to be legitimate research outputs?
- What are the immediate and pressing challenges that alternative publishing platforms are trying to address?
- What are the key barriers faced by alternative publishing platforms?
- What factors affect a researcher's decision to use (or not) an alternative publishing platform?

Both interviews and focus groups will be carried out online via Microsoft Teams. Focus groups will use the software Mentimeter to allow the gathering of structured data in anonymous form (i.e. any information entered by participants will only be available in aggregate form to the research team).

Both interviews and focus groups will be recorded and automatically transcribed (via Microsoft Teams) to ensure accurate representation of the views of participants. Recording and transcription will all take place within secure SharePoint sites and the Microsoft 365 ecosystem managed by Research Consulting. This information in non-anonymous form will only be available to members of the research team.

Transcripts will form the basis of thematic coding, which will be undertaken with support from generative artificial intelligence tools. In particular, the Claude.ai solution will be used to analyse anonymised transcripts. Claude.ai is available to the research team through a paid subscription. Claude.ai does not use data submitted to train their language model, which enables the protection of information provided by participants.

To maintain methodological rigour, the AI-generated themes and patterns will be subject to expert human validation and refinement. A team of researchers will:

- Review the AI-generated themes for accuracy and relevance
- Conduct in-depth interpretation of contextual nuances
- Identify any themes the AI may have overlooked, building on our experience of delivering the interviews and focus groups

This iterative process of AI analysis and human expert review ensures a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the data while significantly reducing the time required for manual coding. It is especially effective given the large number of interviews being conducted, as it will enable us to apply the same systematic approach to the full set of transcripts and notes.

To retain high quality in our AI-assisted research, we will also implement the following measures:

- Inter-coder reliability checks: Multiple human coders will independently review a subset of the AI-analysed data to assess consistency.
- Audit trail: We will maintain documentation of the AI algorithms used, prompts used, and human decision-making processes.

Anonymised quotations of the data will be included as part of a final report to be produced as the final deliverable of this study. This will be a succinct document suitable for public dissemination, focusing on recommendations and key insights emerging from stakeholder engagement activities. This report will be shared openly via an online repository such as Zenodo (to be chosen), using a Creative Commons license. The research team plans to write a peer-reviewed article based on the information collected and shared as part of this project. This will also include anonymised quotations for the data.

The full text of transcriptions of interviews and focus groups will remain confidential. However, anonymised interview extracts will be shared via an online repository alongside relevant thematic codes to illustrate comments made by participants. The anonymised extracts shared will be presented by code but in randomised order, to further prevent the identification of individual contributors.

Personal safety

Have you completed your departmental risk assessment procedures, if appropriate?	Not applicable
Raises personal safety issues?	No Data gathering will take place online.

Section D: About the participants

Potential participants

Interviewees will be drawn from international stakeholders in scholarly communications and will include representatives from research funding organisations, developers of alternative publishing platforms, and selected researchers. Potential interviewees will be a targeted sample, identified in discussion between Knowledge Exchange, Research Consulting and Stephen Pinfield.

Recruiting potential participants

Potential participants will be directly contacted and invited for interview using emails. Reminders will be issued once if no response is received. Participation is entirely optional, and individuals will be able to request not to be contacted further in the context of this study.

Advertising methods

Will the study be advertising using the volunteer lists for staff or students maintained by IT services?	No
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Consent

Will informed consent be obtained from the participants? (ie. the proposed process)	Yes
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Participants will be provided with full information on the project beforehand, in the form of briefing notes. Consent for participation in interviews will be sought verbally and recorded as part of the interview transcript. Consent for participation in focus groups will be sought through an online form.

Payment

Will financial/in kind payments be offered to participants?	No
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Potential harm to participants

What is the potential for physical and/or psychological harm/distress to the participants?	There is very little potential for physical and psychological harm to the participants. The risks of participating are the same as those in everyday life.
How will this be managed to ensure appropriate protection and well-being of the participants?	Data gathering will be conducted in an ethical and professional manner and participants will be able to withdraw at any time whilst data gathering is ongoing.

Potential harm to other who may be affected by the research activities

Which other people, if any, may be affected by the research activities, beyond the participants and the research team?	The recommendations arising from this research may result in new policies that are likely to affect a range of individuals, groups and organisations involved in scholarly communication, including, in the medium and long term, business models of publishers and other service providers.
What is the potential for harm to these people?	Greater adoption of alternative publishing platforms that could arise from the implementation of the recommendations emerging from this research may challenge existing practices and business models currently implemented by organisations in the scholarly communication landscape, meaning they might have to change or tweak their approaches over the long term. Alternative publishing platforms may also challenge existing practices adopted by researchers, meaning that they might have to change their approaches in the long term.
How will this be managed to ensure appropriate safeguarding of these people?	The creation of tailored recommendations by stakeholder group, as well as our broader discussion of the subject in our final report, will enable organisations and individuals taking this work further to do so responsibly and with a clear understanding of the dynamics in the scholarly communication and research landscape. Additionally, this research will engage stakeholders internationally, therefore enhancing the team's ability to take an inclusive approach to the generation of recommendations.

Reporting of safeguarding concerns or incidents

What arrangements will be in place for participants, and any other people external to the University who are involved in, or affected by, the research, to enable reporting of incidents or concerns?	Participants will be given email addresses for the research team to enable reporting of incidents or concerns.
Who will be the Designated Safeguarding Contact(s)?	Stephen Pinfield
How will reported incidents or concerns be handled and escalated?	Reported incidents or concerns will be addressed within the research team where possible; if necessary they can be escalated to the Information School Ethics Leads, or the University's Research Ethics & Integrity Manager. This has been added to the relevant information for participants.

Section E: Personal data

Use of personal data

Will any personal data be processed or accessed as part of the project?	Yes
Will any 'special category' personal data be processed or accessed as part of the project?	No
Provide the number of people whose personal data you expect to process or access.	40

Managing personal data

Which organisation(s) will act as data controller(s) of the personal data?	An external organisation only
What is the name of the external organisation acting as the data controller	Research Consulting LTD
Who will have access to the personal data?	<p>The data will be available to (i) Research Consulting Ltd staff; and (ii) research team members at the University of Sheffield in the first instance on submission. Consent will be obtained from participants for recording, transcription and analysis of the data by Research Consulting and the team at the University of Sheffield.</p> <p>Transcription will be automated using built-in functionality within Microsoft Teams, to ensure the data remains within a legally compliant data ecosystem. Transcripts will then be reviewed and corrected by the interviewers to ensure they accurately reflect the conversation.</p> <p>Participants in the focus groups will have access to personal information about other focus group attendees including name, role titles and organisational affiliation. This will be made clear to focus group participants in advance, and they will be asked for their consent to this as part of the recruitment process.</p> <p>All interview and focus group transcripts will be thematically coded, with any quotes used to underpin the themes aggregated and anonymised prior to sharing in the public domain. This information in non-anonymised form will only be accessible to Research Consulting and the team at the University of Sheffield.</p> <p>Lastly, participants will be asked if they agree to sharing their information within a 'contributors' table as part of the project's final report (e.g. via an Appendix). Any participants who do not agree to sharing their information will be kept anonymous.</p>

	<p>Participants will have the right to withdraw their responses until 1 September 2025.</p> <p>The project funder will only be given access to a stakeholder list covering consultation participants, including basic personal data (e.g. name, role, affiliation, date last contacted, participation status).</p>
What measures, processes and/or agreements will be put in place to manage the personal data?	<p>Personal data collected as part of this study will be stored in Microsoft's SharePoint for Business cloud storage service managed by Research Consulting Ltd. This is a secure password-protected storage facility used to manage the company's confidential data in line with good practice as outlined in its Data Protection & Privacy Policy: https://www.research-consulting.com/privacy/.</p> <p>Any data submitted into Claude.ai will be anonymised and therefore does not fall under the remit of personal data protection.</p> <p>The project funder will only be given access to a stakeholder list covering consultation participants, including basic personal data (e.g. name, role, affiliation, date last contacted, participation status).</p> <p>Access to relevant files will be provided via secure SharePoint links for the duration of this study. Knowledge Exchange will not be given access to transcripts or any other form of personal data that might reflect the views of individual participants.</p>
Will all identifiable personal data in digital or physical format be destroyed within a defined period after the project has ended?	Yes
When will the identifiable personal data be destroyed?	Personal data will be deleted within 24 months of the end of the project.

Third-party services

Will any external third-party services not provided by the University be used to process or access personal data during the project?	Yes
Provide details of each external third-party service.	Data will be stored on Research Consulting Ltd's instance of SharePoint. Analysis of anonymised data will take place using Claude.ai.
Has the University's Information Security team approved the external third-party services you intend to use?	TBC
Has the University's Data Protection team approved any contracts and/or terms and conditions related to the external third-party services?	TBC

Security of computers, devices and software

Will personal data be processed or accessed on any computers or devices that are not managed by the University of Sheffield?	Yes
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Will all computers and devices that are not managed by the University of Sheffield be secured in accordance with the IT Code of Connection?	Yes
Will any software not approved by the University of Sheffield be used to process or access data?	Yes
Will the software be secured in accordance with the IT Code of Connection?	Yes
Will any software be written or developed in order to process or access the personal data?	No

Section F: Supporting documentation

Information and consent

Participant information sheets relevant to project?	Yes
Consent forms relevant to project?	Yes

Additional documentation

None

External documentation

None

Section G: Declaration

Signed by:	Stephen Pinfield
Date signed:	Wed 19 February 2025 12:42

Official notes

None

Participant Information Sheet

Research Project Title

Innovating Scholarly Communication: Navigating the future of Alternative Publishing Platforms

Invitation paragraph

You are being invited to take part in a research project. Before you decide whether or not to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

What is the project's purpose?

The project is exploring the topic of alternative platforms for publishing scholarly research. It will consider means to support innovation in scholarly communication through alternative publishing platforms, seeking insights into the maturity and development of existing and emerging examples.

The research has been commissioned by Knowledge Exchange, a coalition of six national organisations within Europe tasked with developing infrastructure and services to enable the use of digital technologies to improve higher education and research.

This research project will involve a mix of interviews and focus groups with a total of around 40 international stakeholders in scholarly communication. These activities will engage research funding organisations, developers of alternative publishing platforms and researchers.

Why have I been chosen as a possible participant?

You have been invited to participate as a researcher who has used or may use alternative publishing platforms, a representative of a national research funder, a representative of an alternative publishing platform, or someone else with relevant expertise.

Please note the following:

- Researchers and representatives of national research funders will be invited to join an interview
- Representatives of alternative publishing platforms will be invited to join a focus group

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you are advised to keep a copy of this information sheet and to give your consent via email for the research team to analyse the data. A clear statement regarding how we will seek your consent to participate will be available via email prior to our conversation, as part of a briefing note.

You can withdraw from the project at any time up until 1 September 2025. After that point, your submission cannot be removed from the study. If you wish to withdraw from the project, you do not have to give a reason. To withdraw, please contact Stephen Pinfield [address redacted].

Please note that that by choosing to participate in this research, this will not create a legally binding agreement, nor is it intended to create an employment relationship between you and the University of Sheffield.

What will happen to me if I take part? What do I have to do?

If you take part, you will be asked to join an interview or a focus group, based on your affiliation (see point #4 above). We will record some information about you: your name, role, affiliation, email address, and similar professional information. Your personal data will be retained in a confidential form by the research team during the project.

We will record our interview or focus group and transcribe this making use of Microsoft Teams. Your personal data will be analysed in aggregate form, alongside the data arising from other interviews or focus groups. We will share fully anonymised quotes and thematically coded extracts from interviews and focus groups in the public domain, as a project output. These will not be attributed to you or your organisation, and will be in a format that does not allow re-identification.

We will ask you if you agree to optionally sharing your name and affiliation within a 'contributors' table as part of the project's final report (e.g. via an Appendix). Doing so will not mean that your name or organisation is linked to any quotes or extracts from interviews. Any participants who do not agree to sharing their information will be kept anonymous.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

We do not expect there to be any foreseeable discomforts, disadvantages and risks associated with participating in this research, although you should note that extracts from our discussion (whether in an interview or a focus group) will be made publicly available in aggregated and anonymised form.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

While there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that participating will contribute to the development of recommendations that benefit the research community and create a fairer and more equitable research publishing system.

Will my taking part in this project be made public or kept confidential?

Anonymised interview extracts will be made publicly available within our final project reporting and as part of a dataset of anonymised interview extracts illustrating the themes we identify through the research. Your name, role title, and the organisation you work for will not be made public alongside this.

We would like to share your name, role title, and the organisation you work as part of a table of contributors in our final report summarising the findings of this study. You will have full control over this, and we will ask you to confirm whether this is acceptable to you. Should you prefer to remain anonymous, you will have two options: (i) full anonymity; and (ii) name redacted but organisation shared.

This research will also lead to the preparation of a peer-reviewed article. The same considerations noted above apply, as this article would be based on the anonymised coded extract shared in the public domain.

A very small risk will remain of which you ought to be aware that you or your organisation may be identifiable from your response even when anonymised and redacted, although the research team will seek to avoid this.

Your personal data will be retained in a confidential form by the research team during the project so that they can contact you for further information.

The funder will be given access to a list of stakeholders who are being contacted for participation in interviews or focus groups, including your name, role title, and the organisation you work. They will, however, have no access to your non-anonymised contribution.

What is the legal basis for processing my personal data?

Research Consulting Ltd will act as the Data Controller for this study. This means that Research Consulting Ltd is responsible for looking after your information and for using it properly. In order to collect and use your personal information as part of this research project, we must have a basis in law to do so. The basis that we are using is your consent. You may withdraw your consent at any time before 1 September 2025; in that case, your data will be removed from consideration by the project and will be deleted.

You can find more details on Research Consulting's approach to data protection and privacy here:

<https://www.research-consulting.com/privacy/>.

What will happen to the data collected, and the results of the research project?

Your contribution (whether in an interview or a focus group) will be recorded and automatically transcribed through Microsoft Teams. This information will only be available to the research team for analysis purposes.

Your contribution will be analysed through thematic coding. Thematic coding will be supported through the use of generative artificial intelligence, using the Claude.ai platform (using a professional organisational subscription). Please note that only anonymised information would be entered into this platform, and that Claude.ai does not use any of the data we will submit to train their large language model.

Extracts from your contribution corresponding to different themes (whether in an interview or a focus group) will be made publicly available in anonymous form as part of our final project outputs (i.e. as part of a dataset of coded text extracts and, in some cases, as anonymous quotes in our report and peer-reviewed publication, as a way of ensuring that the process is as transparent as possible. However, your name, role title, and the organisation you work for will not be made public alongside these. The sharing of anonymised extracts will take place using an appropriate scholarly communication platform, such as Zenodo or Octopus.ac.

The final outcomes of this research will be published by Knowledge Exchange and the research team in various outputs, including reports, articles and presentations. These will be publicly available and use Creative Commons licences.

Who is organising and funding the research?

This project is funded by Knowledge Exchange.

Who is the Data Controller?

Research Consulting Ltd will act as the Data Controller for this study. This means that Research Consulting Ltd is responsible for looking after your information and for using it properly.

Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project (application no. 066645) has been ethically approved via the University of Sheffield's Ethics Review Procedure, as administered by the Information School.

What if something goes wrong and I wish to complain about the research?

If you are dissatisfied with any aspect of the research and wish to make a complaint, please contact Professor Stephen Pinfield [address redacted] in the first instance. If you feel your complaint has not been handled in a

satisfactory way, you can contact please contact the Information School Ethics Leads, or the University's Research Ethics & Integrity Manager [contact details redacted]. If the complaint relates to how your personal data has been handled, you can find information about how to raise a complaint in the University's Privacy Notice: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/govern/data-protection/privacy/general>.

If you wish to make a report of a concern or incident relating to potential exploitation, abuse or harm resulting from your involvement in this project, please contact the project's Designated Safeguarding Contact (Prof Stephen Pinfield [contact details redacted]). If the concern or incident relates to the Designated Safeguarding Contact, or if you feel a report you have made to this Contact has not been handled in a satisfactory way, you can contact the Information School Ethics Leads or the University's Research Ethics & Integrity Manager [contact details redacted]. Your report should receive a response within 3 working days.

Contact for further information

To obtain further information about the project, please contact:

- Stephen Pinfield or Andrea Chiarelli [contact details redacted].

Thank you for your participation.